

An Overview of Importance of Training- Literature Review

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Abstract

Training needs analysis is the initial step in a cyclical process which contributes to the overall training and educational strategy of staff in an organisation. The cycle commences with a systematic consultation to identify the learning needs of the population considered, followed by course planning, delivery and evaluation. Training presents a prime opportunity to expand the knowledge base of all employees. Employees also miss out on work time while attending training sessions, which may delay the completion of projects. Despite the potential drawbacks, training and development provides both the company as a whole and the individual employees with benefits that make the cost and time a worthwhile investment. This research paper is focused on Importance & evaluation of training. Training employees is an essential activity for all organisations. Training provides employees with the knowledge and skills they need to perform their job.

Key Words:-

Importance, Need, Evaluation, Process, Benefits & Classifications.

Introduction

Today's work environment requires employees to be skilled in performing complex tasks in an efficient, cost-effective, and safe manner. Training (a performance improvement tool) is needed when employees are not performing up to a certain standard or at an expected level of performance. The difference between actual, the actual level of job performance and the expected level of job performance indicates a need for training. The identification of training needs is the first step in a uniform method of instructional design. A successful training identify those who need training and what kind of training is needed. It is counter-productive to offer training to individuals who do not need it or to offer the wrong kind of training. A Training Needs Analysis helps to put the training resources to good use. The secondary data were collected for the purpose of study.

Objectives of the study

- a) To understand the importance given to training in industries.
- b) To understand the need of training for improving skills and competency of employees in industries.
- c) To know about the various techniques to evaluate training program.

Training

Definition:-

Dale S. Beach stated “Training as ‘the organized procedure by which people learn knowledge and/or skill for a definite purpose’. Training refers to the teaching and learning activities carried on for the primary purpose of helping members of an organization acquire and apply the knowledge, skills, abilities, and attitudes needed by a particular job and organization.”

Edwin Flippo stated “Training is the act of increasing the skills of an employee for doing a particular job’

Importance of Training

1. To Increase the Productivity:- Increased human performance often directly leads to increased operational productivity and increased company profit. This productivity can be increased by instructions. Increased performance and productivity, because of training are most evident on the part of new employees who are yet fully aware of the most efficient and effective ways of performing their jobs.

2. To Improve Quality of Work:- Better informed workers are less likely to make operational mistakes. Improvement in quality may be in relation to company’s product/ service or employment atmosphere.

3. To improve Health and Safety:- Proper training can help prevent industrial accidents. A safer work place leads to more stable mental attitudes on the part of employees. Managerial mental state would also improve if supervisors know that they can better perform themselves through company designed development programmes.

4. Out datedness Prevention:- Training and development programmes foster the initiative and creativity of employees and help to prevent manpower obsolescence, which may be due to age, temperament or motivation or the inability of a person to adapt himself to technological changes.

5. To Improve Organizational Climate:- An endless chain of positive reactions results from a well planned training programme. Production and product quality may improve, financial incentives may increased , less supervisory pressures may result. Increased morale may be due to many factors, but one of the most important of these is the current state of an orga'nistion's educational endeavor.

6. Personal Growth:- Management development programmes seem to give participants a wider awareness, and enlarged skill, and enlightened altruistic philosophy and make enhanced growth possible.

7. To Assist a company to fulfilling its Future:- Organisations that have a good internal educational programme will have to make less drastic manpower changes and adjustments in the even of sudden personnel alterations. When the need arises, organizational vacancies can more easily be staffed from internal sources if a company initiates and maintains adequate instructional programme for both it s non-supervisory and managerial employees.

8. Help in addressing employee weaknesses:-Most workers have certain weaknesses in their workplace, which hinder them from giving the best services. Training assists in eliminating these weaknesses, by strengthening workers skills. A well organized development program helps employees gain similar skills and knowledge, thus bringing them all to a higher uniform level. This simply means that the whole workforce is reliable, so the company or organization doesn't have to rely only on specific employees.

9. Improvement in workers performance:-A properly trained employee becomes more informed about procedures for various tasks. The worker confidence is also boosted by training and development. This confidence comes from the fact that the employee is fully aware of his/her roles and responsibilities. It helps the worker carry out the duties in better way and even find new ideas to incorporate in the daily execution of duty.

10. Ensuring worker satisfaction:-Training and development makes the employee also feel satisfied with the role they play in the company or organization. This is driven by the great ability they gain to execute their duties. They feel they belong to the company or the organization that they work for and the only way to reward it is giving the best services they can.

11. Reduced cost:-Training and development results with optimal utilization of resources in a company or organization. There is no wastage of resources, which may cause extra

expenses. Accidents are also reduced during working. All the machines and resources are used economically, reducing expenditure.

12. Reduction in supervision:-The moment they gain the necessary skills and knowledge, employees will become more confident. They will become self reliant and require only little guidance as they perform their tasks. The supervisor can depend on the employee's decision to give quality output. This relieves supervisors the burden of constantly having to give directives on what should be done.

Employee Training

Training employees is an essential activity for all organisations. Training provides employees with the knowledge and skills they need to perform their job.

Source- [www. Learnmanagement2.com](http://www.Learnmanagement2.com)

Benefits of Training

- As the business world is continuously changing, organisations will need to provide their employees with training throughout their careers. If they choose not to provide continuous training they will find it difficult to stay ahead of the competition.
- The other benefit of training is that it will keep your employees motivated. New skills and knowledge can help to reduce boredom. It also demonstrates to the employee that they are valuable enough for the employer to invest in them and their development.
- Training can be used to create positive attitudes through clarifying the behaviours and attitudes that are expected from the employee.

- Training can be cost effective, as it is cheaper to train existing employees compared to recruiting new employee with the skills you need.
- Training can save the organisation money if the training helps the employee to become more efficient.

Induction Training

This is training that an employee will receive when they first join an organisation or begin a new role. This type of training is designed to provide the employee with the essential skills needed to perform their job. Induction training can also include an introduction to the company ethos, values and culture so that the employee is aware of the behaviours expected of them.

On the Job Training

As the name suggests, on the job training, is training provided during the regular performance of duties. This can take a variety of forms including

- **Guidance**:-The employee being guided through a task or process by a colleague or supervisor, so that the employee knows how to perform the task and to what standard.
- **Shadowing**:-Spending time with an expert so that the employee can observe how the expert performs their daily duties.
- **Observations**:-The employee is observed whilst they perform their duties. At the end of the observation, the observer will provide the employee with feedback on their performance and a training plan based on the results from the observation.
- **Coaching**:-The idea behind coaching is to improve the employee's existing skills, (or to provide them with new skills) by focusing on how the employee performs something i.e. there is a focus on technique. Coaching provides employees with the opportunity to practice skills with a coach away from their usual work environment.
- **Mentoring**:-The employee is partnered with an experienced employee so that they can discuss performance. The experienced person is known as the mentor and the employee they are partnered with we will call the mentoree. The mentoree will discuss their performance and problems with the mentor.

- **Computer Based Training:**-Some firms will use a computer based (digital app) to provide training. Computer based training usually involves providing the employee with relevant information followed by quizzes to test how well the employee has learnt the information.

Off the Job Training

This is training provided away from the employee's usual work environment. Off the job training may be in the same building or off site. This training may be provided by trainers working for the same employer as the employees being trained or an outside company hired by the employer. Off the job training is often used to support the employees studying for a formal qualification or exam. In contrast to coaching this type of training usually focuses on knowledge and not skills.

Training Need Classification

Source:-<http://www.slideshare.net/hemanthcrpatna/a-project-report-on-training-and-development-with-special-reference-to-sahara-india>

a. Organizational Level:-

Training need analysis at organizational level focuses on strategic planning, business need, and goals. It starts with the assessment of internal environment of the organization such as, procedures, structures, policies, strengths, and weaknesses and external environment such as opportunities and threats.

After doing the SWOT analysis, weaknesses can be dealt with the training interventions, while strengths can further be strengthened with continued training. Threats can be

reduced by identifying the areas where training is required. And, opportunities can be exploited by balancing it against costs.

However, individual competence can also be linked to individual need. The methods that are used to analyse the individual need are:-

- Appraisal and performance review
- Peer appraisal
- Competency assessments
- Subordinate appraisal
- Client feedback
- Customer feedback
- Self-assessment or self-appraisal

b. Individual Level :-

Training need analysis at individual level focuses on each and every individual in the organization. At this level, the organization checks whether an employee is performing at desired level or the performance is below expectation. If the difference between the expected performance and actual performance comes out to be positive, then certainly corporate need and training need are interdependent because the organization performance ultimately depends on the performance of its individual employee and its sub group.

c. Operational Level:-

Training Need analysis at operational level focuses on the work that is being assigned to the employees. The job analyst gathers the information on whether the job is clearly understood by an employee or not. He gathers this information through technical interview, observation, psychological test; questionnaires asking the closed ended as well as open ended questions, etc. Today, jobs are dynamic and keep changing over the time. Employees need to prepare for these changes. The job analyst also gathers information on the tasks needs to be done plus the tasks that will be required in the future.

Evaluation of Training Program

The process of examining a training program is called training evaluation. It checks whether training has had the desired effect. Training evaluation ensures that whether candidates are able to implement their respective work places or to the regular work routine.

1. Immediate:-This relates to changes in knowledge, skill or behavior immediately after a training experience. In other words, it attempts to assess

- Whether or not, training has been effective in communication the message.
- Have people learned the skill you were setting out to teach?
- Do they understand what is now required to them?
- Have they been equipped with the necessary behavior to be able to implement the learning.

2. Intermediate:- This refers to evidence that knowledge, skill and behavior which has been learned is being put into use on the job. In other words, can the trainee, manager and colleagues identify changes in behaviours, skill and attitude as a result of the trainee's attendance.

3. Long Term:- This refers to the long-term effectiveness of the individual. The unit and perhaps even the organization. This ultimate evaluation is difficult and only possible if the training in the first instance has been related to the real corporate strategic and business needs of the organization. What the trainer is attempting to evaluate is, does the individual now make a real contribution to the business needs of the organization, or has training just been a comfortable and hopefully enjoyable experience which has brought about little change?'

Evaluation is about determining the value of the training delivered. It should seek to assess:

- i. The effectiveness of the training
- ii. The effectiveness of the learning process – in other words. Whether the trainees have learned what we set out to teach them.
- iii. Whether the learning has been applied.
- iv. Whether the applied learning has brought about the changes required in relation to attitudes, skill or behavior.

If trainers can begin to think about evaluation within the context of the three phases outlined above, it should be possible to design and apply a range of evaluation techniques appropriate to each phase. Of course, many techniques will be appropriate to all phases, but some will apply primarily to one or the other.

It is often assumed that it is relatively easy to assess knowledge gain. However, what is often overlooked is retention levels. Ask any students two months after a major exam to remember the learning at the level they achieved just prior to the examination; you will find that retention level is directly related to the method and purpose of learning and the activity participated immediately afterwards, and much of the learning may well have been lost.

Therefore, while it may well be possible to assess and measure knowledge gain effectively, it is more important for the trainers to assess retention and application levels.

Purpose of Training Evaluation

The five main purposes of training evaluation are:

- a. Feedback:** it helps in giving feedback to the candidates by defining the objectives and linking it to learning outcomes.
- b. Research:** it helps in ascertaining the relationship between acquired knowledge, transfer of knowledge at the work place and training.
- c. Control:** It helps in controlling the training program because if the training is not effective, then it can be dealt with accordingly.
- d. Power games:** At times, the top management (higher authoritative employee) uses the evaluative data to manipulate it for their own benefits.
- e. Intervention:** It helps in determining that whether the actual outcomes are aligned with the expected outcomes.

Process of Training Evaluation

Before Training

The learner's skills and knowledge are assessed before the training program. During the start of training, candidates generally perceive it as a waste of resources because at most of the times candidates are unaware of the objectives and learning outcomes of the program. Once aware, they are asked to give their opinions on the methods used and whether those methods confirm to the candidates preferences and learning style.

Source:- <http://www.naukrihub.com/trainings/training-evaluation.html>

During Training

It is the phase at which instruction is started. This phase usually consist of short tests at regular intervals

After Training

It is the phase when learner's skills and knowledge are assessed again to measure the effectiveness of the training. This phase is designed to determine whether training has had the desired effect at individual department and organizational levels. There are various evaluation techniques for this phase.

Conclusion

Continuous employee training is essential as it ensures your employees always have the knowledge and skills to work effectively. In fact some professions such as medicine and law stipulate that practitioners have to perform a minimum number of continuous professional development. Having a good staff of people is not the only requirement of today's scenario rather they need to be polished with their skills by giving them certain required trainings. So finding the need of training in any organization is very essential and accordingly designing the training program. I came to know the detail about What this company is all about, what is its basic functions, what services it provides to the customers, how it sales its product and makes profit out of it. The suggestion I would suggest regarding the training of the people in the company is that various training programs should organized in regular intervals of time so as to develop their overall personality such as their attitude, perception as well as various training regarding communication skills as well as soft skill related training should be organized so as to make them fluent while talking with their customers. Training related to Customer Relationship Management as well as Data Management System should be given. Retraining and refreshment trainings should be provided to them so that if they have some doubt in the actual training then they can get it clear or if they have got outdated during the course of time because of various scientific and technological changes, so it would make them up to date with relevant knowledge required for that particular job. One of the important things that would help the sales people to deal easily with their customers as well as to attract them is to provide the training for differentiating the products with that of their competitors so that if a customers asks them that why should he purchase his product and not that of other Brand than they should be able to deal with their queries easily. A good training program provides comfortable environment and job satisfaction for the employees. Training plays a vital role for the development of the enterprise. It brings out new talents who are capable of having good basic knowledge of the enterprise and its objectives. This will make the organization to get profited from the employees as well as they also get attractive benefits from the organization for their

performance in the form of incentives, bonus and promotions. This would motivate the employees and hence the growth of the company will be a steady one.

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